

Project management (PM) and Operational plan (OP)

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Placemus XR consortium

No.	Short name	Institution name	Country
1	CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche	Italy
2	CHANGES	Fondazione CHANGES- Cultural Heritage active Innovation for Sustainable Society	Italy
3	CNRS	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique CNRS	France
4	UT	Université de Tours	France
5	MF	Mezzo Forte	France
6	OU	The Open University	UK
7	Hangvető	Hangveto Zenei Terjeszto Tarsulaskorlatolt Felelossegu Tarsasag	Hungary
8	GEOFolkLife	GEORGIA Folk Life	Georgia
9	3DR	3D Research Srl	Italy
10	SD	S.D. Cinematografica	Italy
11	PK/CUT	Politechnika Krakowska	Poland
12	COBO	Comune di Bologna	Italy
23	BCM-BGIR	Ministero della Cultura	Italy
14	MdV	Museo del Violino	Italy

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

AR	Augmented Reality
CA	Consortium Agreement
EB	Executive Board
ECCCH	European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage
ECHOES	European Cloud for Heritage OpEn Science project
GA	Grant Agreement
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
MIM	Mutual Insurance Mechanism
NDA	Non-Disclosure Agreement
RMP	Risk Management Plan
SAB	Stakeholders Advisory Board
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
VR	Virtual Reality
WP	Work Package
XR	Extended Reality

1. The Project Handbook

The Project Handbook reports the management processes for communication, monitoring, approval of deliverables adopted within the PlaceMUS XR project, including the setting up of guidelines, templates and standards.

Benefits of creating a Project Management Plan include:

- clear definition of roles, responsibilities, processes and activities.
- increased probability that project will be completed on time, within budget, and with high-quality results.
- ensure that decision making processes are clear and participated.
- help project partners plan project activities and their management (scheduling, quality, risk management, etc.).

It also provides the necessary indications to define the overall managerial strategy and how each phase established by the PlaceMUS XR documentation must be made operational, within a dedicated timeframe, during the project implementation.

The current text constitutes is a living document, constantly evolving with attention to the progression of overlapping parallel tasks of WPs and their deliverables.

The intended target of the PlaceMUS XR Project Handbook consists of members of the PlaceMUS XR Consortium and the Project Officer(s).

2. Project Summary

This research project focuses on creating digital applications that enable users to explore significant “PLACES of MUSic” across European regions and cities. The applications aim to provide an interwoven narrative, encompassing the musical event itself, its cultural and historical context, the location, and physical museum objects. This multi-layered storytelling approach will draw upon a diverse range of sources, including musical scores, instruments, chronicles, diaries, letters, philosophical treatises, and images.

The project involves geographically mapping musical locations and creating engaging thematic itineraries based on places, people, themes, and historical periods, encompassing a wealth of tangible and intangible heritage. It will be implemented through case studies which will be further adaptable and extensible in the future.

The project will focus on developing cutting-edge digital tools to enrich the visitor experience at these places of music through virtual and augmented reality experiences, multimedia accessible through different applications and tools integrated in the ECCCH. This includes a particular emphasis on reconstructing historical soundscapes, as well as the acoustic properties of spaces for musical performances, exploring the interplay between music and architecture, and harnessing the potential of virtual and augmented reality technologies. Furthermore, the project will create design and simulation tools, conduct analysis and evaluation of the users' interactions with content and digital tools, as well as the impact of audio-visual communication in museums.

To achieve these aims, the project will cater to a diverse audience, encompassing scholars, museum curators, the entire educational sector, creative cultural industries, citizens and tourists.

All datasets, metadata, and interaction tools will be Open Source and implemented in accordance with the FAIR principles, aligning with the knowledge base and requirements of the ECCCH.

3. Project objectives

The PlaceMUS XR project, whose leading theme is “Paths and Places of Music in Europe” interpreted as extended realities, focuses on developing cutting-edge digital tools, to be integrated in the ECCCH, aimed at integrating cultural contexts and heritage objects in the users' experience. They include several types of material objects/contexts as well as intangible heritage, whose value, possibilities of interaction and understanding are enhanced by virtual reality technologies and digital tools. Design and simulation tools will be implemented to 1) create, share,

re-use, interactive contents, 2) analyse, design and verify interaction with visitors, for the benefit of museum curators, creative industries, students, and researchers.

The vast panorama of musical genres and their related places and objects will be exemplified in the project through a selection of musical itineraries and places in cities or regions that have been, or are, representative of musical life and culture. The efficiency of the organisational models and developed tools, both in terms of dataset modelling, open science practices, and innovative ICT solutions aiming at users' interaction will be measured and verified through case studies that foresee a threefold narrative: 1) of the musical event; 2) of the cultural context; 3) of the place to which the music is connected.

PlaceMUS XR proposes the virtual reintegration of various musical forms within their original context using a variety of sources: i) musical pieces (derived from discography and from live musical performances recording); ii) reading or scripting chronicles of musical events; iii) stories, diaries, and letters from musicians, patrons, and travellers; iv) significant passages from philosophical treatises on the theme of music and its interlink with other arts; v) viewing dances or ceremonies contextualised in significant locations, derived from historical archives or recorded in the present; vi) all tangible signs that are still legible in the urban environment today.

The overarching goal is to cultivate a deeper appreciation of places of music and their historical, cultural, and artistic context, providing users with interactive experiences engaging at cognitive, aesthetic and emotional levels, through Virtual and Augmented Reality and multimedia contents, which they can access online from anywhere (digital experience) or while visiting the real sites along paths (phy-gital experience). Platforms and tools developed will not only be used to visualise and interact with the content of case studies produced by the project. They will be open tools designed to create and share new interactions, scenarios, content, stories, exhibits, both expanding the presented case studies or developing new scenarios by using digital data stored in the ECCCH or in other compatible EU platforms.

The activities focus on eight research, technological, and societal objectives (OBJ), based on the interdependence of humanities, social sciences, and computer science domains, as detailed below in Table 1 - List of project objectives:

OBJECTIVE	RELATED WP	OBJECTIVE DESCRIPTION
OBJ-01	WP10, WP11	To create, share and re-use scenarios, contents, exhibits and improve interactions with places and objects of music
OBJ-02	WP5, WP6, WP10	To analyse, design and test the interactions with visitors
OBJ-03	WP3, WP15, WP7	To design and create itineraries and places of music as Extended Realities
OBJ-04	WP7	To foster a deeper understanding of sound, architectural forms and space
OBJ-05	WP5, WP11	To create a VR Mock-up tool to design sound communication in museums
OBJ-06	WP4	To create and promote accessible solutions for extended interaction with places of Music
OBJ-07	WP8, WP9	To develop, share, re-use dataset and tools in accordance with ECCCH
OBJ-08:	WP12, WP13, WP14	To provide guidelines and training modules to promote methodologies and best practices of PlaceMUS XR

Table 1 - List of project objectives

4. Project synergies

Within the project WP12 and WP13, clustering activities have been envisaged to establish continue and fruitful collaboration with similar or linked projects and two deliverables will be released on these activities, D12.5 *Clustering Activities Report I* (M15) and D13.1 *Clustering Activities report II: Networking with ECCCH and EU similar projects* (M36).

In the first instance, these activities will involve projects financed by the European Commission to help build and enrich the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH), among which the following can be identified:

- [ECHOES](#) - European Cloud for Heritage OpEn Science is preparing the main Cloud infrastructure.
- The 3 projects will provide tools for the Cloud users:

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- [AUTOMATA](#) - AUTOMated enriched digitisation of Archaeological liThics and cerAmics
 - [TEXTaiLES](#) - TEXTile digitisAtion tooLs and mEthodS for cultural heritage
 - [HERITALISE](#) - Heritage buildings and objects' digitisation & visualisation within the cloud
- The 10 sister projects financed under the 2024 ECCCH call:

Digitalisation and analysis of dynamic processes, objects and complex combined data

- [KINETIKA](#) - Advancing the Digitization and Analysis of Dynamic Cultural Heritage Objects
- [MusicSphere](#) - A Multimodal Approach for Digitizing, Analyzing, and Simulating Traditional Musical Organs Through 3D Technologies, Acoustic Analysis and Interactive Experiences

Advanced data enrichment

- [INFINITY](#) - Multidimensional knowledge-based annotation for ethical context-aware heritage data life cycles
- [ECHOLOT](#) - European Cultural Heritage Optimised Linked Open Tools

Documenting, interlinking and organising data

- [ARXIVE](#) - Advanced Research and eXploration for Interoperable Value in European Heritage
- [StratiGraph](#) - Knowledge Graphs for Stratigraphy

High-value interactions with visitors and heritage objects

- [UNICHE](#) - Unified No-Code platform for Interactive Cultural Heritage Experiences, under the same call of [PlaceMUS XR](#)

Study, conservation and restoration of heritage objects

- [EXCALIBUR](#) - Advanced toolkits for interdisciplinary and enhanced study, conservation, and restoration in burial excavations and findings
- [COLOURS](#) - Collaborative On-cloud Lab for the conservation and digital restoration of ColOUred heritage collectionS

A continue and fruitful collaboration aiming at reaching a wider impact on EU cultural landscape will be also implemented with other similar or linked national

and EU projects and networks, such as [Mary4ALL](#), [Voicing Spaces](#): Towards an Aural Architecture in the Past, etc.), to share lessons learned and best practices.

Another cooperation has been established with the COST Action [Early MUSE](#) - A new ecosystem of early music studies, regarding Musicology, Early music, Music education, Performance studies, and Creative industries.

The cooperation with the SAB will allow to identify further projects and national and international initiatives that will be engaged in the clustering activities.

5. Project timeline

PlaceMUS XR is a 48-month long project, starting on the 1st of October 2025 and ending the 30th of September 2029. Three reporting periods are envisaged, at M17, M36 and M48. The timeline and related expected deliverables submission is shown in Figure 1 - Project GANTT.

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Figure 1 - Project GANTT

6. Project resources

The project budget, in the form of lump sum, amounts to € 3.967.333,26.

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The € 2.117.866,70 prefinancing, net of the 5% Mutual Insurance Mechanism (MIM) share, has been distributed among partners as shown in Figure 2 - Project Resources

		BUDGET	% BUDGET	PREFINANCING	MIM	ACTUAL TRANSFER
BE1	CNR	861.603,18 €	21,72%	459.946,41 €	43.080,16 €	416.866,25 €
BE2	CHANGES	571.149,80 €	14,40%	304.894,77 €	28.557,49 €	276.337,28 €
BE3	CNRS	364.490,96 €	9,19%	194.574,85 €	18.224,55 €	176.350,30 €
BE4	UT	342.507,50 €	8,63%	182.839,50 €	17.125,37 €	165.714,13 €
BE5	MF	303.087,09 €	7,64%	161.795,85 €	15.154,35 €	146.641,50 €
BE6	OU	257.882,83 €	6,50%	137.664,63 €	12.894,14 €	124.770,49 €
BE7	Hangvető	149.231,26 €	3,76%	79.663,57 €	7.461,56 €	72.202,00 €
BE8	Georgia Folklife	255.525,00 €	6,44%	136.405,96 €	12.776,25 €	123.629,71 €
BE9	3DR	450.007,54 €	11,34%	240.225,84 €	22.500,38 €	217.725,47 €
BE10	SD	145.410,60 €	3,67%	77.624,00 €	7.270,53 €	70.353,47 €
BE11	PK/CUT	266.437,50 €	6,72%	142.231,34 €	13.321,87 €	128.909,46 €
		3.967.333,26 €	100,00%	2.117.866,70	198.366,66 €	1.919.500,04 €

Figure 2 - Project Resources

The two interim payments (90 days from receiving periodic report) can sum up to 90% of the maximum grant amount and the final payment (90 days from receiving final report) will be calculated by deducting the total amount of prefinancing and interim payments already made from the final grant amount. The amount retained for the MIM will also be released and paid (if not used).

7. Project governance

7.1 The PlaceMUS XR Consortium

The PlaceMUS XR Consortium, coordinated by the Institute of Heritage Science (ISPC) and with the participation of the Institute of Information Technologies (ISTI- Artificial Intelligence for Media and Humanities Lab) and Institute of Marine Engineering (Acoustics and Sensors "OM Corbino" Research Unit) of the National Research Council of Italy (CNR) is composed by 11 partners, including research and academic institutions (CNR, CNRS, UT, OU, PK/CUT), creative industries (MF, 3DR, Hangvető, SD), a cultural Foundation (CHANGES) and a cultural association aiming at preserving and promoting extraordinary and unique musical heritage which is gradually disappearing from contemporary practices (GEORGIA FOLK LIFE).

CNR also has 3 Associated Partners that will play a crucial role in the PlaceMUS XR project.

The Music Archive of the **Complesso monumentale e Biblioteca dei Girolamini** (BCM-GIR) in Napoli is one of the most important repositories of Baroque music in the world.

The **Museo Internazionale e Biblioteca della Musica** (COBO) in Bologna, houses one of the most prestigious collections in terms of printed music repertoire from the 16th to the 18th centuries, and an impressive collection of painting and musical instruments, especially keyboard ones.

The **Museo del Violino** (MdV) in Cremona protects and promotes the value of classical and contemporary Cremonese violin making (UNESCO Heritage), through exhibitions, conferences, publications, auditions with historical instruments and concerts.

7.2 Project governance

The project governance is mainly related to the activities envisaged in WP1 and WP2. These activities will be under the responsibility of CNR in its role as Coordinator, with the support of CHANGES and the participation of the whole Consortium and some partners in specific tasks (i.e. 3DR in T1.5 and T2.5 and Hangvető in T1.6 and T2.6) and include: monitoring the proper implementation of the action; act as the intermediary between the consortium and the granting authority; distribute the payments received from the granting authority to the other beneficiaries without unjustified delay. The coordinator, assisted by the Executive Board (EB), will be the main responsible also for the scientific monitoring and reporting, including Risks Management and quality assurance, as well as for the implementation of corrective actions, if needed.

Following the signature of the Grant Agreement (GA), the first steps carried out at the beginning of the project have been: 1) the drafting of a Consortium Agreement (CA) to ensure a successful project implementation and to provide guidelines to resolve intellectual property right (IPR) issues (further detailed in Deliverables D1.10 IPR Management Plan due at M17 and Deliverable D2.5 Final version of IPR Management Plan due at M45); 2) Project Kick-off meeting; 3) the appointment of

the Stakeholders Advisory Board and the signature of the Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA) by its members.

The coordinator and the Executive Board (EB) have organized an operational plan that has been approved by the General Assembly (GA) during the project kick-off meeting and has been used as the starting point for the drafting of this Project Handbook. This operational plan includes: i) the tentative scheduling and agenda distribution timing of 4 GA meetings; ii) the tentative scheduling and agenda distribution timing of the EB online meetings; iii) preliminary detail of the main conferences to be attended to disseminate the project results; iv) the tentative scheduling and agenda distribution timing of meetings with the Stakeholder Advisory Board (SAB); vi) the development and refinement of the Data Management Plan (DMP); v) the setting up of the PlaceMUS XR Open Access Repository.

7.3 Roles and responsibilities

The project is organised in different Bodies with different specific functions (Table 2 - Project Bodies) to facilitate the scientific/technical/management activities and organisation. The PlaceMUS XR governance structure is illustrated in Figure 3 - Project Governance:

Figure 3 - Project Governance

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ROLE	FUNCTION
<p>The project Coordinator</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Acts as intermediary between the Parties and the European Commission. - Chair all the meetings of the General Assembly and the Executive Board. - Monitor the proper overall technical implementation and management of the project. - Request and review any documents or information required and verify their quality and completeness before passing them on to the granting authority. - Submit the deliverables and reports to the granting authority. - Reports to the Executive Board, the General Assembly and the European Commission. - Distribute the payments received from the granting authority to the other beneficiaries without unjustified delay.
<p>The Executive Board</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Composed by the Coordinator, Work Package Leaders. - Assisting the coordinator in monitoring progress towards expected deliverables, milestones and risk management. - Responsible for the implementation of corrective actions, if needed. - Gathering information from Beneficiaries and WPLs. - Drafting project reports for approval by the General Assembly
<p>WP Leaders</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coordinate the completion of activities for the tasks in the relevant Work package. - Check the quality of the deliverables related to their WP.
<p>The General Assembly</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Composed by at least one representative from each beneficiary. - Is the main decision-making body. - Responsible for the overall implementation of the project.
<p>Beneficiaries</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Must keep information stored in the Portal Participant Register up to date. - Inform the granting authority (and the other beneficiaries) immediately of any events or circumstances likely to affect significantly or delay the implementation of the action.

	<p>– Submit to the Coordinator/WP Leaders in good time the contribution to the deliverables and technical reports.</p>
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Table 2 - Project Bodies

7.4 The Stakeholders Advisory Board (SAB)

The project bodies will be supported by a board of external advisors, the Stakeholder Advisory Board (SAB), that will be composed by 12 members from European and international organisations holding a stakeholder’s role in the CH sector. Their fields of expertise range from GIS to musicology, ethnomusicology, programming, sound studies, data modelling, policy analysis in creative industries and accessibility.

The SAB can make recommendations on the project implementation, which must be considered by the General Assembly and, in order to do so, it is involved in the GA meetings to be constantly updated about the project. Furthermore, project deliverables will be submitted to those members of the SAB whose background and expertise are relevant to the subject of the document, so to have a continuous feedback, recommendations and hints on possible corrective actions.

8. Project Work Packages (WPs) and Tasks leaders

The PlaceMUS XR WPs, interconnected as shown in Figure 4 - PlaceMUS XR WPs interrelation, are led by the WP and Task Leaders listed in the table below (Table 3 - WPs and Tasks Leaders)

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Figure 4 - PlaceMUS XR WPs interrelation

WPs/TASKS	DESCRIPTION	LEADER (Affiliation)
WP1	Coordination and Management	Eva Pietroni (CNR)
T1.1	Governance, Scientific coordination	Eva Pietroni (CNR)
T1.2	Creation and Communication with Stakeholders Advisory Board (SAB)	Daniela Maria Palamà (CNR)
T1.3	Project monitoring	Eva Pietroni (CNR)
T1.4	Risk Management and quality assurance	Eva Pietroni (CNR)
T1.5	Data Management Plan	Daniela Maria Palamà (CNR)
T1.6	Ethical and Gender Equality issues	Daniela Maria Palamà (CNR)
T1.7	IPR Management	Daniela Maria Palamà (CNR)
WP2	Coordination and Management	Eva Pietroni (CNR)
T2.1	Governance, Scientific coordination	Eva Pietroni (CNR)

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T2.2	Creation and Communication with Stakeholders Advisory Board (SAB)	Daniela Maria Palamà (CNR)
T2.3	Project monitoring	Eva Pietroni (CNR)
T2.4	Risk Management and quality assurance	Eva Pietroni (CNR)
T2.5	Data Management Plan	Daniela Maria Palamà (CNR)
T2.6	Ethical and Gender Equality issues	Daniela Maria Palamà (CNR)
T2.7	IPR Management	Daniela Maria Palamà (CNR)
WP3	Itineraries and Scenarios	Eva Pietroni (CNR)
T3.1	Scenarios and Itineraries Requirements and Criteria	Camilla Cavicchi (UT)
T3.2	Design of case studies & collection of existing resources	Maria Taloni (CNR)
WP4	Accessibility of Media and Tools	Simon Holland (OU)
T4.1	Accessibility of digital media	Roberto Dall'Angelo (SD)
T4.2	Accessibility-oriented artificial intelligence	Roberto Dall'Angelo (SD)
T4.3	Haptic tool and interface for accessible engagement with Rhythm	Simon Holland (OU)
T4.4	Gestural tool and interface for accessible engagement with Harmony	Simon Holland (OU)
T4.5	Tools and interfaces for accessible engagement with Tuning	Enzo d'Annibale (CNR)
T4.6	Multisensory representation of information sets: Specifications, designs and methods	Jean-Yves Blaise (CNRS)
T4.7	Visual mapping of acoustic data	Jean-Yves Blaise (CNRS)

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T4.8	Acoustic mapping of visual data	Jean-Yves Blaise (CNRS)
T4.9	Deployment of tools and data sets	Jean-Yves Blaise (CNRS)
T4.10	Accessibility of tools to create scenarios by stakeholders	Paola Di Cuia (3DR)
WP5	PRELIMINARY User studies - Analyses and Design of Interactions	Camilla Cavicchi (UT)
T5.1	Preliminary Survey: Methodology and tools	Ivana Cerato (CNR)
T5.2	Preliminary Survey: development, Data analyses and interpretation	Camilla Cavicchi (UT)
T5.3	User Experience Design	Eva Pietroni (CNR)
T5.4	Design of the Digital Mockup online VR Tool to design sound communication in museums	Paola Di Cuia (3DR)
WP6	VERIFICATION User studies – test of interactions	Barbara Pucci (CHANGES)
T6.1	Verification Survey: Methodology and tools	Ivana Cerato (CNR)
T6.2	Verification Surveys: Development, Data analyses and interpretation	TBC (3DR)
T6.3	Creation of a Community Map	Nana Mzhavanadze (GEOFolkLife)
WP7	Digitisation and Audio-Visual Content Production	Jean-Yves Blaise (CNRS)
T7.1	Spatial-acoustic acquisition protocols	Marco Liuni (MF)
T7.2	Spatial-acoustic data acquisition	Marco Liuni (MF)

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T7.3	Maps and cartography prototype for itineraries and places of music	Jean-Yves Blaise (CNRS)
T7.4	Places of Music 360 representation	Enzo d'Annibale (CNR)
T7.5	Places of Music and objects 3D representation	Diego Ronchi (CNR)
T7.6	Audio-visual storytelling	Roberto Dall'Angelo (SD)
T7.7	Atlas of sonic heritage gestures associated with sounds	Nana Mzhavanadze (GEOFolkLife)
WP8	INTEGRATION INTO THE ECCCH – Analysis	UT Philippe Vendrix
T8.1	Knowledge base & Data Model in connection with ECCCH requirements	Augustin Braud (UT)
T8.2	Metadata formalism	Romano Aloisi (3DR)
T8.3	Experience Ontology	Person to be hired (CNR)
WP9	INTEGRATION INTO THE ECCCH - Implementation	Romano Aloisi (3DR)
T9.1	Dataset migration and integration strategies	Romano Aloisi (3DR)
T9.2	Integration	Romano Aloisi (3DR)
T9.3	Testing of developed tools integrated in ECCCH and assessment	Domenica Dininno (CNR)
WP10	Platforms & Tools Development for The Creation, Re-Use, Sharing of Interactive Scenarios	Alessandro Lupinacci (3DR)
T10.1	Story Map Building and Visualising Tool	Valentina Bartalesi (CNR)

T10.2	GeoVIZ: interactive thematic geovisualisation tool	Jean-Yves Blaise (CNRS)
T10.3	Open-Source Web3D Scene Editor framework	Salvatore Isabella (3DR)
T10.4	Open-Source Web3D Presentation Layer framework	Alessandro Lupinacci (3DR)
T10.5	Immersive Analytics Open-Source Web Services	Bruno Fanini (CNR)
T10.6	Sound Augmented Experiences framework - Agami	TBC (MF)
WP11	PLATFORMS & TOOLS DEMOSTRATORS Implemented with PlaceMUs-XR Case Studies	Marco Liuni (MF)
T11.1	Web app: VR Mock-up Tool to design exhibitions and sound communication in museums	Bruno Fanini (CNR)
T11.2	PlaceMUS XR Web Portal & Virtual Museum	Ailin Arimand (UT)
T11.3	PlaceMUS XR On the Move	Marco Liuni (MF)
T11.4	Museum demonstrators and gamification	Salvatore Isabella (3DR)
T11.5	Metaverse	Alessandro Cozza (3DR)
WP12	Communication strategies and first steps	Sara Venczel (Hangvető)
T12.1	Communication and Dissemination Plan	Ivana Cerato (CNR)
T12.2	Internal communication strategy	Barbara Pucci (CHANGES)

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T12.3	Communication strategy towards external audiences	Ivana Cerato (CNR)
T12.4	Scientific communication strategy	Sara Venczel (Hangvető)
T12.5	Publication of Guidelines for Communication strategies on historical soundscapes	Elisa Dalla Longa (CNR)
WP13	Dissemination and Exploitation and final events	Barbara Pucci (CHANGES)
T13.1	Towards wider general audience	Sara Venczel (Hangvető)
T13.2	Towards scientific community	Camilla Cavicchi (UT)
T13.3	Public events to consolidate prototypes	Sara Venczel (Hangvető)
T13.4	Networking, Sister & Cousins projects	Sara Venczel (Hangvető)
T13.5	PlaceMUS XR Final exhibits in museums and in places of Music	Fabio Beltotto (CHANGES)
T13.6	Publication of PlaceMUS XR <i>Know How Book</i>	Maria Taloni (CNR)
T13.7	Exploitation Strategies	Ilaria Manzini (CHANGES)
WP14	Training	Klaudia Stala (PK/CUT)
T14.1	Know-how Webinars	Klaudia Stala (PK/CUT)
T14.2	Training on PlacesMUS XR expansion and tools re-use	Alessandro Lupinacci (3DR)
WP15	ITINERARIES AND SCENARIOS II Storytelling	Elisa Dalla Longa (CNR)
T15.1	Storytelling	Eva Pietroni (CNR)
T15.2	Narratives visualized as story maps, supported by Semantic Web	Valentina Bartalesi (CNR)

Table 3 - WPs and Tasks Leaders

9. Risk management

The possible risks related to the project implementation have been identified and detailed in Annex 1 – Part A of the Grant Agreement (p. 55) and are shown in the following Table 4 - Critical risks & risk management strategy.

As risk assessment and management is an ongoing process that requires adaptive measures, a dedicated set of deliverables (*D1.3 – Risk Management Plan, M6, D1.4 Mid-term version of RMP, M17, D2.1 Mid-term version of RMP, M36, D2.2 Final version of RMP, M48*) has been envisaged in WP1 and WP2, with the dual purpose of monitoring the project, ensuring the quality of results, and implementing corrective actions if necessary. The RMP will be structured as follows: i) Description of the risk management process to be adopted; ii) List of all project risk types, iii) Risk analysis matrix with severity and probability of occurrence; iv) Risk response plan (prevention, mitigation or transfer); v) List of people responsible for risk management.

<u>Critical risks & risk management strategy</u>			
Risk number	Description L (i)=likelihood, (ii)=severity: Low/Medium/High	Work Package No(s)	Proposed Mitigation Measures
1	A partner leaves the consortium (i) L-(ii) L	WP2, WP1	The Consortium will reassign impacted tasks among other partners or will find a replacement with existing contacts
2	A partner does not perform according to work plan and/or budget (i) L-(ii) H	WP2, WP1	Close monitoring of progress using project indicators and budget consumption by PM so to identify non-active partners. A chance to recover will be given to them, notifying the EC. If no improvement can be seen, the budget can be moved to other partners carrying out additional activities, or, in the worst case, EB will ask partner to leave the consortium.

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3	Insufficient consortium Coordination & competence /effectiveness (i) L-(ii) M)	WP2, WP1	The appropriate consortium management is assured via the Project Management described in WP1. The roles and responsibilities of each partner are identified and shall continuously be monitored to mitigate the risk of overlapping implementation of the same activities from two or more partners.
4	Poor communication between partners, leading to divergence among project partners on strategic priorities. (i) L-(ii) M)	WP2, WP1	The consortium agreement will provide the basis for resolving conflicts that arise between partners. Decision- making by consensus will be the priority; however, after a reasonable amount of time has been allowed to present and debate conflicting positions, the approval of a majority of Partners will be sufficient to confirm a management decision.
5	Inaccessibility of some places of music (i) L - (ii) M	WP3	A choice of 7 itineraries on 10 proposed.
6	Use of existing resources (places, discography, archival data) to be paid (i) L - (ii) L	WP3	Use of free resources; agreements with owners; payment of limited cost; use of resources from involved partners/ stakeholders. Involvement of musical schools/ensembles for new recordings
7	AI open-source algorithms for Virtual Avatar in Sign Language not well refined; expensive license fee of commercial solutions (i) L -(ii) M	WP4	More than one solution will be tested and special agreement with developers will be proposed, even for temporary use. Low costs license can be paid.
8	AI open-source algorithms for Text to Speech not well refined. Expensive license fee of commercial solutions (i) L -(ii) M	WP4	More than one solution will be tested and special agreement with developers will be proposed. Low costs license can be paid.
9	Difficulty to extensive application of Multisensory representation of information sets, as it's a complex work (i) L - (ii) H	WP4	It will be applied to one case study: Cracow itinerary. Methodological pipeline will be shared on ECCCH and on project web portal.

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10	Prototypes for engagement with Rhythm, Harmony and Tuning are museum installations, they can be partially shared online (i) L -(ii) L	WP4	Prototype Design, Methodological pipeline and technical features will be shared on ECCCH and on project web portal
11	Partner's difficulties in conducting preliminary survey with identical approach, comparisons of results could be not impartial (i)M – (ii)M	WP5	Instructions to partners will be delivered by the WP and task leader through online meeting, written guidelines and template.
12	Partner's difficulties in analysing and interpreting results of survey with identical approach, results could be not impartial (i)M –(ii)M	WP5	Original data coming from users must be available on reserved repository for verification and final alignment.
13	Partner's difficulties in conducting verification survey with identical approach, comparisons of results could be not impartial (i)M – (ii)M	WP6	Instructions to partners will be delivered by the WP and task leader through online meeting, written guidelines and template.
14	Partner's difficulties in analysing and interpreting results of survey with identical approach, results could be not impartial (i)M–(ii)M	WP6	Original data coming from users must be available on reserved repository for verification and final alignment.
15	Noisy environment disturbing recording. (i) L - (ii) M	WP7	Digitisation activities in the night/quiet moments. Ask for permissions to stop noise if feasible. Choose another place.
16	Impossibility to carry out detailed 3D scanning. (i) L - (ii) L	WP7	Different digitisation levels of accuracy are possible, even faster 360°.
17	Lack of homogeneity in the aesthetic quality and technical requirements of 360° views acquired from different partners. (i) M - (ii) M	WP7	Detailed technical guidelines will be shared among partners and iterative internal online meeting will be organised for verification
18	Lack of homogeneity in the aesthetic quality and technical requirements of 3D models acquired from different partners. (i) M - (ii) M	WP7	Detailed technical guidelines will be shared among partners and iterative internal online meeting will be organised for verification

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19	Gaps in production workflows and scant coordination among partners, delay in delivery. (i) M - (ii) H	WP7	Clear divisions and connections of work among partners since the beginning. Constant monitoring of activities carried out by the WP leader and coordination team. Any changes in production chain will be in time.
20	High costs for hosting, managing, populating and maintaining infrastructure. (i) M - (ii) H	WP8, WP9	H2IOSC Data Center, managed by CNR ISPC in Lecce, will provide hosting. The cost of a fixed-term researcher has been included in the project budget. After the project end, we'll need to update strategy.
21	The ECCCH infrastructure and ECHOES' guidelines are not yet complete and operational at the end of this project. (i) L - (ii) H	WP8, WP9	Granularity of PlaceMUS XR knowledge base will be flexible and will depend on the ECCCH's evolving architecture. Possible extensions will be evaluated. We shall focus on modular designs which can be updated and refined.
22	The PlaceMUS XR dataset and tools are not fully compatible with all EU Cloud platforms. (i)M-ii) M	WP8, WP9	PlaceMUS XR will adopt open standards, following ECHOES guidelines. Metadata will facilitate production of content to be shared also on other EU platforms and data spaces.
23	Data Center for storage and management of resources is not available from the beginning of the project. (i) M - (ii) L	WP8, WP9	PlaceMUS XR database and tools will be created on a local server, and they will be migrated, integrated and tested on a Data Center Infrastructure before the end of the project.
24	Excessive development effort in relation to the duration of the project. (i) L - (ii) M	WP10	SW development is distributed among 5 partners (CNR-ISPC, CNR-ISTI, CNRS, MF, 3DR). Most of the tools already exist, effort will be addressed to enrichment and integration.
25	ICT partners working alone on their own tool. Lack of shared methods and tool chains. (i) L- (ii) M	WP10	Internal meeting will be organised to share strategies and approaches since the beginning of the project. ICT Partners will cooperate in tools development, considering distributions of their effort expressed in the GANNT. This

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			shows propensity to integrate tools.
26	Technical difficulty to integrate tools. (i) L- (ii) L	WP10	Most of tools are designed around modern and robust web standards. (R 01.2), (R 01.3), (R 01.4), (R 01.5) in WP10, and (R 01.8) in WP11 are based on ATON. MINERVA is built on ATON with possible extensions in Unity 3D. SMBVT uses standard Ontologies, i.e., CIDOC CRM, LRMoo and OWL Time.
27	Technical difficulty to integrate tools in ECCCH. (i) L- (ii) L	WP10	Most of tools are designed around modern and robust web standards compliant with ECCCH. They are already integrated in Open EU and national research infrastructure (e.g. E-RIHS Digilab-IT). ECHOES's guidelines will be respected.
28	Difficulties to design a fluid and coherent User Experience using many tools. (i) L- (ii) L	WP10	Tools have many functionalities and modules, sometimes redundant. Modules are scalable, they can be chosen and combined with flexibility to design coherently the desired kind of experience.
29	Low number of effective uses of the VR Mockup tool by stakeholder. (i) M- (ii) M	WP11	Museums and Library partners will be involved in the tool design and test, to adapt it as much as possible to their needs. External stakeholders and SAB will be invited for testing and evaluation, aiming at further improvement and dissemination
30	Limited time to implement all itineraries in the tools. (i) L- (ii)M	WP11	Many partners are involved in implementation of demonstrators. SW development will use PlaceMUS XR ongoing resources.
31	Difficulties of logistics and scheduling of final exhibition in Museums. (i) L- (ii) L	WP11	We can choose among three associated partners' venues. Organisation will start well in advance, since month 12.

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32	Licensing high costs of the Metaverse platform. (i) L- (ii) L	WP11	Many platforms will be evaluated; licensing could be paid for few months for dissemination purposes. Alternative use of ATON will be considered to create the Metaverse.
33	Lack of engagement from consortium members. (i) L-(ii) M	WP12	Ensure clear communication about the importance of active participation.
34	Inadequate reach of external communication efforts. (i) -(ii) L	WP12	Utilise a variety of communication channels (website, social media, press releases, events).
35	Delays in publication of deliverables (i) L - (ii) M	WP12	Regularly monitor progress and address any potential delays promptly.
36	Limited impact of the "PlaceMUS on the Road" initiative. (i) -(ii) L	WP12	Develop engaging and accessible storytelling approaches for the initiative.
37	The public may not be sufficiently engaged with the project's storytelling and demonstrations, limiting the reach and impact of these activities. (i) L - (ii) M	WP13	Develop highly engaging and interactive content that caters to diverse audiences.
38	Difficulties in engaging SMEs effectively. (i) L-(ii) L	WP13	Offer tailored support and resources to facilitate SME involvement.
39	Delays in producing the PlaceMUS XR Know-How Book. (i) L - (ii) M	WP13	Establish a clear timeline and assign responsibilities for each stage of the book's development.
40	Limited reach and impact of Metaverse presentations. (i)L-(ii)L	WP13	Promote the Metaverse events widely through targeted marketing and social media campaigns.
41	Low attendance and engagement in training activities (i) M - (ii) M	WP14	Ensure the training content is relevant, engaging, and tailored to the needs and interests of the target audience.
42	Technical difficulties or limitations with online training platforms (i) L - (ii) L	WP14	Thoroughly test the online training platform before launch to identify and address any technical issues.

Table 4 - Critical risks & risk management strategy

10. Conflict Resolution

The Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement will provide the basis for resolving conflicts that arise between partners. Decision-making by consensus will be the priority; however, after a reasonable amount of time has been allowed to present and debate conflicting positions, the approval by the majority of Partners will be sufficient to confirm a management decision.

The Partners agree to abide by all decisions of the General Assembly. This does not prevent the Parties from exercising their veto rights, according to Section 6.2.4.1, or from submitting a dispute to resolution in accordance with the provisions of Settlement of disputes in Section 11.8 of the CA.

The Coordinator shall provide guidance and support to all partners in the resolution of possible conflicts that may arise during the implementation of the project and will be supported in this role by the Executive Board.

11. Internal Project communication

11.1 Internal communication

A smooth communication within the project is crucial to facilitate the work of partners and to avoid misunderstanding, poor dissemination of information and delays on the activities.

Emails and the Microsoft Teams[®] Channels will be the daily tools of communication among partners, as the only meetings in person planned in the GA are the yearly General Assembly meetings.

Concerning emails, the following labelling rule has been identified:

Label the email by entering the name of the project and the relevant work package in square brackets in the subject line, followed by a specific description of the email's content.

Example: [PlaceMUS XR - WP12] next appointment and deadlines

11.1.1 Contact list

The coordinator oversees the setting up and the update of mailing lists that will be structured as follows:

- General Mailing list: all the project participants.
- Executive Board mailing list: addressed to all the members of the EB.
- General Assembly mailing list: addressed to the main scientific contacts of each Partner.
- WPs mailing list: addressed to the participants to each WP.
- Communication&Editorial Board list: addressed to the persons (at least one per partner) involved in board responsible for Communication and Dissemination activities.
- SAB mailing list: addressed to the members of the SAB.

11.2 Project Meetings

Meetings should be organized regularly at WP and task levels to define and plan activities, discuss progress and assign responsibilities, share ideas, clarify questions or doubts.

WP and Task meetings will be held via Microsoft Teams®.

In general, remote meetings should be scheduled at least one week in advance, have a set agenda and produce minutes which will allow tracking of actions items. The Copilot® app will be used to record the meetings, so to facilitate the drafting of minutes and to give the opportunity to people unable to participate to have access to the full content of the meeting.

The scheduling of the meetings and the meeting minutes are under the responsibility of each WP/Task Leader. A first scheduling of the WP Meetings has been planned (Table 5 - WPs Meetings calendar), for those WPs that have already started their activities.

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	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	WP8	WP9	WP10	WP11	WP12	WP13	WP14	WP15
WP meetings frequency	Every 2 months the the first Wednesday of the month.	TO BE PLANNED WHEN ACTIVITIES START	Monthly on the first Tuesday of the month	First Tuesday of every month	Monthly on the first Thursday of the month	Monthly on the first Friday of the month	TO BE PLANNED WHEN ACTIVITIES START	TO BE PLANNED WHEN ACTIVITIES START	Monthly on the second Monday of the month	Monthly on the first Tuesday of the month	TO BE PLANNED WHEN ACTIVITIES START	Bimonthly on the first Wednesday at 11am	Monthly on the third Friday of the month	Monthly on the first Wednesday of the month at 10 am	Bi-weekly
Time and estimated duration	10:00 - 11:15 am CET (45 minutes+ max 30' for discussion)	TO BE PLANNED WHEN ACTIVITIES START	2:30 - 3:45 pm CET (45'+30' for discussion)	3:00 - 4:00 pm CET (central European time) for 1 hour	2:30 - 3:45 pm CET	12:00 - 13:15 CET	TO BE PLANNED WHEN ACTIVITIES START	TO BE PLANNED WHEN ACTIVITIES START	11:00 - 12:00 (CET)	11:00 - 12:00 (CET)	TO BE PLANNED WHEN ACTIVITIES START	11:00 - 12:00 am CET	12:00 - 13:15 pm CET	10:00 - 11:30 CET	1 hour + max 0.5 hours for Q&A
Starting date	28th January 2026	TO BE PLANNED WHEN ACTIVITIES START	3rd February 2026	3rd February 2026	12th February 2026	3rd March 2028	TO BE PLANNED WHEN ACTIVITIES START	TO BE PLANNED WHEN ACTIVITIES START	8th October 2027	6th October 2026	TO BE PLANNED WHEN ACTIVITIES START	16th December 2025	17th March 2027	2nd April 2029	12th January 2027

Table 5 - WPs Meetings calendar

The project governing bodies will meet on a regular basis, as established both in the GA and the CA, so to ensure the proper implementation of the activities, assess the progress, share results, plan future activities and handle potential critical issues.

The **General Assembly** will meet in presence once a year in 4 different partners' countries, with the possibility of extraordinary meetings at any time upon request of the Executive Board or 1/3 of the Members of the General Assembly. The meeting will be held in presence, but remote connection will be provided for the General Assembly, the SAB and the EB sessions, in order to allow the widest possible participation of the Consortium members and the advisors.

The **Executive Board** will meet online at least twice a year with periodic updates every 2 month, with the possibility of extraordinary meetings at any time upon request of any member of the Executive Board.

The notice of meeting will be given in written form by the chairperson of the Consortium Body as follows:

- 45 calendar days before for ordinary meetings of the General Assembly
- 15 calendar days for extraordinary meetings
- 14 calendar days before for ordinary meetings of the Executive Board
- 7 calendar days for extraordinary meetings.

The agenda of meetings will be prepared and shared as follows:

- 15 calendar days before for ordinary meetings of the General Assembly

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- 7 calendar days for extraordinary meetings
- 7 calendar days before the meetings of the Executive Board.

Any agenda item requiring a decision by the Members of a Consortium Body must be identified as such on the agenda. Any Member of a Consortium Body may add an item to the original agenda by written notice to all the other Members of that Consortium Body.

Meetings of each Consortium Body may also be held by tele- or videoconference, or other telecommunication means.

The **Stakeholder Advisory Board** will be invited to the 4 periodic meetings of the General Assembly, including the kick-off. The SAB members can attend meetings **in person or in remote**.

Participation to each annual meetings will include six SAB members in presence and six in remote, rotating, to give equal participation opportunities to all members. The participants' costs will be refunded by the Consortium.

The **Associated Partners** will be invited to the project meetings and, not having a budget within the project, will cover the travel costs with their Institution's budget.

The meeting minutes include: Header with indication of WP and related task; useful documents to be considered in the meeting; date, agenda, participants and their organisation; apologies for those ones unable to attend; Main objective, Discussion & Updates report; Cross-WP Collaborations & Dependencies; Action Items & Next Steps to be performed; Upcoming Milestones & Deliverables.

11.3 Document repository

Microsoft Sharepoint® has been selected as the repository for the project, as it allows users to work collectively on a number of documents and to save them automatically, enabling efficient

and fluid collaboration between the various partners and members of the project, and to store and share files. Each channel within a team has its own file folder.

11.4 Online collaboration platform

The online collaboration platform chosen by the partners is Microsoft Teams®. After analysing a few options, it has been identified as the favourite one as it allows at the same time smooth communication, file sharing and conference calls organisation and management, including meeting reporting.

The platform has been structured in different channels, a General one, with documents and information of shared use and interest, and one channel for each WP.

Each channel contains the “Posts”, “Shared” and “WP Calendar” tabs. “Posts” shall be used for communication related to the channel’s topic (Figure 5 - PlaceMUS XR Microsoft Teams® structure).

Figure 5 - PlaceMUS XR Microsoft Teams® structure

The “Shared” tab gives access to the SharePoint folder (and sub-folders) connected to the individual channel, where a subfolder for each task is created with the

deliverables, dataset and documents of interest for carrying out the activity (Figure 6 - PlaceMUS XR Teams® channel structure WPs).

Figure 6 - PlaceMUS XR Teams® channel structure WPs

Channels are open to all Consortium Partners to allow everyone a complete overview of the project progression. However, to avoid overload of communications, working groups related to each WP have been created in Outlook Office, and e-mail communication regarding the WP activity are addressed only to the participants.

11.5 PlaceMUS XR Visual Identity

WP12 and WP13 are dedicated to the project communication both internally and with the external audience. Although the communication strategy will be detailed in D12.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan, the first steps for building up the project visual identity have been undertaken since the early phase of PlaceMUS XR.

Following the guidelines received from the ECHOES project on co-branding, the following project logo has been created (Figure 7 - Project logo)

Figure 7 - Project logo

In order to ensure consistency in the visual identity of the project, templates were also created for presentations and letterhead, as shown in Figure 8 - Presentation Template and in Figure 9 - Letterhead template

Figure 8 - Presentation Template

Figure 9 - Letterhead template

The PlaceMUS XR website domain has been activated (placemus-xr-eccch.eu), the structure and the mock-up of the main web pages are defined, and text content realised. The site is currently under development, as a milestone of WP12.

12. Project reporting

As established in Art. 21.1 of the Grant Agreement, the beneficiaries must provide regular updates on the status of the project and on the progress of the action through the Portal Continuous Reporting tool (Figure 10 - EU Portal Continuous Reporting section) in accordance with the timing and conditions it sets out and as agreed with the granting authority.

The **Continuous Reporting** includes¹:

- progress in achieving **milestones**, defined by the EC as “*Control points in the project that help to chart progress (kick-off meetings, steering committees, first-draft of a survey, prototype, etc.) They may correspond to the completion of a key deliverable, which allows the next phase of the work to begin, or is needed at intermediary points.*”

¹ <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/funding-tenders-opportunities/spaces/OM/pages/1867968/Continuous+reporting+on+milestones+deliverables>

- **Deliverables**, defined by the EC as “*Outputs to be submitted to the EU (publication, leaflet, progress report, brochure, list, etc.)*”
- updates to the **publishable summary**
- response to **critical risks, publications, communications activities, IPRs**

Figure 10 - EU Portal Continuous Reporting section

Further to the Continuous Reporting activity, a **Periodic Report** must be submitted directly in the Periodic Reporting Module of the Portal Grant Management System according to the scheduling set out in the Grant Agreement to receive payments (M17, M36 and M48).

The periodic report should be prepared by the consortium participants together and submitted by the Coordinator and must detail the progress of the work and costs claimed. When the Coordinator submits the periodic report, the IT tool will capture the information from the Continuous Reporting Module to generate the Technical Report. It consists of two parts:

- Part A: contains the structured tables with project information (retrieved from the Grant Management System).
- Part B: the narrative part, mirrors the application form and requires the participants to report on differences (*delays, work not implemented, new subcontracts, budget overruns etc.*) It must be uploaded as PDF document.²

The technical report details who did what at the level of the participating organisations, indicating the contributions from beneficiaries, associated partners, and subcontractors.

² <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/funding-tenders-opportunities/spaces/OM/pages/1867970/Reports+and+payment+requests>

Based on the status of the Work Packages and the amounts of lump sum shares attributed to each beneficiary in the grant agreement per WP, the Financial Statement for all beneficiaries is automatically generated and a notification will be sent to the Coordinator that the Financial Statement is ready to be signed.

12.1 Internal monitoring

The internal monitoring of the progress of activities is undertaken by the WP leaders, that will inform with no undue delay the Coordinator of any possible criticality.

The Coordinator will organise periodic meeting every 2 months (or more frequently if needed) with all WP leaders who will refer about the state of advancement of their WP and possible criticalities.

A deliverables assessment process has been envisaged to allow a thorough quality-check, and it is structured in 2 Levels.

- The 1st review will be carried out by the relevant WP Leader, that receives the document by the Task Leader according to the agreed schedule.
- The 2nd review will be carried out by the EB, that will receive the deliverable 15 days before the deadline and will have 10 days to submit its comments and remarks, if any. The EB will review the overall quality of the product, with its members with a deeper knowledge of the subject contributing more in depth on the specific matter, providing written feedback within the expected deadline.

13. References

- European Commission, *Model Grant Agreement Lump Sum Grants*, Version 1.0, 01 November 2024
- European Commission, *EU Grants: How to manage your lump sum grants*, V1.4, 15 October 2025
- European Commission, *EU Grants: AGA — Annotated Grant Agreement*, V1.0, 01 May 2024
- Project: 101233325 — PlaceMUS XR — HORIZON-CL2-2024-HERITAGE-ECCCH-01 Grant Agreement
- Project: 101233325 — PlaceMUS XR Consortium Agreement
- <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/funding-tenders-opportunities/spaces/OM/pages/1867968/Continuous+reporting+on+milestones+deliverables>

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Annex 1 – Kick-off meeting agenda